

Abstract**A multi-institutional descriptive study of bone and soft tissue cancers by age, sex and site in northeastern Nigeria**

Onota P.O¹, Ezenkwa U.S¹, Rufai Y¹, Suleiman D.E², Kabir A³, Kolomi M.A⁴, Adamu I.A⁵, Muhammad M⁶, Lawan A.I⁷

Author Affiliations

¹Department of Histopathology, Federal University of Health Sciences/Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria

²Department of Histopathology, College of Medical Sciences, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi State, Nigeria

³Department of Histopathology, College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri/University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital, Borno State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Pathology, Federal Medical Centre Nguru, Yobe State, Nigeria

⁵Department of Histopathology, Yobe State University/Yobe State University Teaching Hospital, Yobe State, Nigeria

⁶Department of Surgery, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare

⁷Department of Histopathology, College of Medical Sciences, Gombe State University/Federal Teaching Hospital, Gombe State, Nigeria

Corresponding author: Priscilla O. Onota. Department of Anatomic Pathology, Federal University of Health Sciences/Federal Medical Centre, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

Phone number: +2347069378692, Email address: onotaometere@gmail.com

Background

Bone and soft tissue cancers (BSTC), though less common than benign tumours, require prompt diagnosis due to high mortality. Disparities in diagnostic tools and underreporting in underserved areas hinder understanding and effective intervention. This study presents multi-institutional data on BSTC in north-eastern Nigeria and suggests strategies to address these issues.

Materials and Methods

Histopathological data from six tertiary hospitals in north-eastern Nigeria, spanning four years (January 2019 to December 2022),

were reviewed. Cases diagnosed as bone and soft tissue cancers (STC) were analysed using summary statistics and Kruskal-Wallis tests to determine proportions and age differences, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

BSTC accounted for 187 (4%) of 4681 histologically diagnosed cancers, with a male-to-female ratio of 2.6:1, a median age of 25 years (interquartile range, 26 years), and a peak in the second decade. Seventy-five cases (39.9%) involved bone, and 113 (60.1%) were STC. Osteosarcoma (43, 23%) was the most common, followed by rhabdomyosarcoma (32, 17.1%). Osteosarcoma and rhabdomyosarcoma predominated among children (35/50, 70%) and in the first three decades (53/96, 55.2%). In older age groups, metastatic carcinomas (12/82, 14.6%) and other tumours were common. 19 cases (10.2%) lacked histological subtype classification. Age distribution differences were significant between patients with bone cancer (median 22.5 years) and those with STC (median 31 years), as well as between children and adults ($p = 0.025$, < 0.001 , respectively). However, no significant differences were observed between genders ($p = 0.263$).

Conclusion

BSTC appear rare in this population, predominantly affecting younger individuals, likely reflecting demographic trends. Early diagnosis and effective population-based registries are essential for effective intervention and data reporting.

Keywords: Bone and soft tissue, cancers, north-eastern Nigeria

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0)

Copyright: The Author(s). 2025

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18910320>

Date Submitted: 20th November 2025

Date Accepted: 2nd March 2026

Date Published Online: 10th March 2026

Cite this article as: Onota P.O¹, Ezenkwa U.S¹, Rufai Y¹, Suleiman D.E², Kabir A³, Kolomi M.A⁴, Adamu I.A⁵, Muhammad M⁶, Lawan A.I⁷ A multi-institutional descriptive study of bone and soft tissue cancers by age, sex and site in northeastern Nigeria. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; S2-9.